

H²IOSC

Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud

Visual identity **GUIDELINE**

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Editorial Board

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RIS IT NODES LOGOS

CLARIN-IT
DARIAH-IT
E-RIHS.it
OPERAS-IT

COMMUNICATION KIT

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Genetics

TIPOGRAPHY

H2IOSC fonts is **Titillum** or in alternative **Titillum Web**. Titillum is a free font designed by Accademia di Belle Arti di Urbino. Titillum and all its derivations are published under SIL Open Font License, Version 1.1.

Titillum Web

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii
Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr
Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz
0123456789 #@&!?

Thin

Light

Regular

Italic

SemiBold

Bold

Black

Download **Titillum Web**

Genetics

TIPOGRAPHY | FONT USAGE EXSAMPLE

TITLE
REGULAR →

Accelerating the digital transformation

SUBTITLE
BOLD →

H2IOSC: the Italian digital ecosystem for open and participatory humanities research

BODY
TEXT
REGULAR →

Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud (H2IOSC) is a pioneering project funded by the European Union Next Generation EU and the Italian Ministry of University and Research as part of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP).

Colour

PRIMARY COLOURS

H2IOSC visual identity has two main colours: **indigo dye**, a dark blue and **polynesian blue**, the emblematic blue of the European Union. These colours must be used for general and institutional communications, such as news, events, presentations and others.

← This colour is indicated by the MUR guidelines for NRRP beneficiaries to indicate the **MISSION “Education and Research”**

In addition to the main colours, the **white** and the **uranian blue** are used as **neutral colours to balance** the other institutional primary colours in the institutional communications.

ADDITIONAL COLOURS (ICON’S LOGO COLOURS)

INDIGO DYE
HEX 07426E
RGB 7, 66, 110
CMYK 94, 40, 0, 57

LAPIS LAZULI
HEX 006699
RGB 0, 102, 153
CMYK 100, 33, 0, 40

RED (CMYK)
HEX EA212D
RGB 234, 33, 45
CMYK 0, 86, 81, 8

PALATINATE
HEX 6A2462
RGB 106, 36, 98
CMYK 0, 66, 8, 58

Logo

MAIN LOGO

H2IOSC logo consists of **three elements**. The icon, the wordmark and the payoff. The full logo should only appear in full colour. In no way should the logo be modified, redrawn and distorted. The font used in the wordmark and in the payoff is the **Basic Commercial SR Pro**.

[Download **Basic Commercial SR Pro**](#)

Logo

SECONDARY LOGO

The secondary logos have **very restrictive usage**. It can only be employed in:

- **social media** where the main logo cannot fit the layout
- **graphic materials** created for initiatives in which the H2IOSC project is involved as a participant where the main logo cannot fit the layout

The secondary logos consist of **three varieties** that guarantee H2IOSC visibility without compromising the recognizability and its identity.

COMPACT HORIZONTAL

ICON + WORDMARK

COMPACT VERTICAL 1

ICON + WORDMARK

COMPACT VERTICAL 2

WORDMARK + PAYOFF

Logo

USAGE RULES

Logo clear space

To ensure the right breathing space for the logo use a square of 5mm as shown below.

Minimum size

7 cm
width
→

4 cm
width
→

3.5 cm
width
→

2 cm
width
→

Logo

POSITIVE & NEGATIVE

Logo

INCORRECT LOGO USAGE

Download **LOGO H2IOSC**

Funding logos

MAIN LOCKUP

Under the NRRP a **signature logo must be present in every document**, in the foreground, always clearly visible.

The **signature logo** consists of the following elements, and must follow this hierarchy:

- the European Union emblem, with the specific “Funded by the European Union NextGenerationEU ”
- the Italian Ministry of the University and Research Logo
- the government logo of the NRRP “Italiadomani”
- the beneficiary logo

EXAMPLE: CORRECT USE OF FUNDING LOGOS

1

2

3

4

 Download **Funding logos**

 Download **MUR Guidelines**

Acknowledgement

USAGE RULES

Any document that is created under the H2IOSC project and is made public, including notices, tenders, certificates, fact sheets, research reports, information events, etc., **must include** a statement (**acknowledging**) that the action was funded by NRRP.

The following are the Italian and English versions, extended version and short version, of the **acknowledging** to be included in the made public documents created as part of the H2IOSC project.

VERSIONE ITA

Versione estesa

Progetto H2IOSC - Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud finanziato dall'Unione europea NextGenerationEU - Piano Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza (PNRR) - Missione 4 "Istruzione e Ricerca" Componente 2 "Dalla ricerca all'impresa" Linea di Investimento 3.1 "Fondo per la realizzazione di un sistema integrato di infrastrutture di ricerca e innovazione" Azione 3.1.1 "Creazione di nuove IR o potenziamento di quelle esistenti che concorrono agli obiettivi di Eccellenza Scientifica di Horizon Europe e costituzione di reti" - Codice progetto IR0000029 - CUP B63C22000730005. Soggetto attuatore CNR.

Versione breve

Progetto H2IOSC - Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud finanziato dall'Unione europea NextGenerationEU - PNRR M4C2 - Codice progetto IR0000029 - CUP B63C22000730005.

Acknowledgement

ENG VERSION

Long version

H2IOSC Project - Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud funded by the European Union NextGenerationEU - National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP) - Mission 4 "Education and Research" Component 2 "From research to business" Investment 3.1 "Fund for the realization of an integrated system of research and innovation infrastructures" Action 3.1.1 "Creation of new research infrastructures strengthening of existing ones and their networking for Scientific Excellence under Horizon Europe" - Project code IR0000029 - CUP B63C22000730005. Implementing Entity CNR.

Short version

H2IOSC Project - Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud funded by the European Union – NextGenerationEU – NRRP M4C2 - Project code IR0000029 - CUP B63C22000730005.

RIs IT Nodes logos

MAIN LOCKUP

In the H2IOSC project communication, the **logos of each RIs Italian node** should be included, when necessary. It is important, to ensure that the logos used are not those of the European infrastructure but are those characterising the national nodes.

The RIs IT Nodes consists of the following logos:

- CLARIN-IT
- DARIAH-IT
- E-RIHS.it
- OPERAS-IT

CORRECT USE OF RIS IT NODES LOGOS

1

2

3

4

Download **RIs IT Nodes logos**

Contact

For any further information or support please contact

Editorial Board

editorial.board@h2iosc.cnr.it

Communication kit

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